

The Effect of Social Media Addiction on Student Phubbing Behavior

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ABSTRACT: Phubbing is a phenomenon that occurs due to technological developments without realizing it occurs in student interactions in everyday life. This study wanted to find out whether there was a relationship between social media addiction and phubbing behavior among college students. The hypothesis proposed is that there is a relationship between social media addiction and phubbing behavior. This research uses quantitative research methods with correlational research type. The research data collection was carried out using a questionnaire method. Respondents were selected by the purposive sampling technique. The number of samples used as research subjects was 65 participants. The results of data analysis show that the correlation coefficient is (r) 0.311 with sig. 0,000 ($p < 0.01$). This study concludes that there is a positive relationship between social media addiction and phubbing behavior. The higher the social media addiction, the higher the phubbing behavior. The contribution of social media addiction to phubbing behavior was 19.7%. While the remaining 80.3% is another factor not included in the study.

KEYWORDS -Social Media Addiction, Phubbing Behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, the internet has contributed greatly to almost all over the world. Especially in this reform era, everyone can use and utilize the internet for various purposes [1]. One of them is the facility for the use of social media which has become a global phenomenon. Through social media, many people are united in virtual space even though they are geographically far apart. Social media is also a convenient place for individuals to share personal information, interact in cyberspace with friends from the real world, and even meet many people based solely on shared interests [2,3]. The results of the Indonesian Polling study together with the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) in collaboration with the Indonesia Survey Center (ISC) taken during the 2019-2020 period stated that internet usage per second quarter reached 73.3% of the population or the equivalent of 196.7 million users. The results prove that there is an increase of 8.9% or the equivalent of 25.5 million internet users in Indonesia. The results of APJII also highlight the behavior of internet users, especially the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic, where the majority access the internet for more than 8 hours a day. The user's favorite social media platforms are Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and Whatsapp. The development of technology and the digital world seem to be the driving force for the phubbing phenomenon [4, 5].

Phubbing was born from a combination of the words phone and snubbing. Phubbing is defined as the behavior of disregarding other people in social interactions because they are more focused on their cellphones. Phubbing perpetrators are called phubbers, namely people who constantly check their cellphones such as social media or chatting. The Phubbing phenomenon is rife at all ages, both young and old. However, this phenomenon is more often experienced by the younger generation. Phubbing is also defined as the behavior of someone who becomes very dependent on cellphones and becomes less concerned about their surroundings. Phubbing can lead to a series of negative consequences, such as lower levels of more serious conversations [6, 7] and depression [8, 9, 10]. Many people feel disappointed and aggrieved by phubbing actors so that a statement appears that cellphones bring distant and distant ones closer.

The younger generation, especially students nowadays, tend to be more engaged in playing gadgets than interacting directly with their social environment. Phubbing actors are usually those who spend a lot of time on the internet, so they only have very little time to communicate with other people in real terms. They

depend their lives on gadgets for various reasons such as helping with assignments, seeking knowledge, looking for reading sources, following developments, etc. But without realizing it, dependence on gadgets that they consider to be a support for their studies or as followers of their development can become an obstacle to their studies if they are not used according to their actual function and wisely.

Problematic social media use, also known as social media addiction, is defined as an unhealthy and excessive form of social media use characterized by a lack of control over behavior and continued behavior despite adverse life consequences [11]. According to the usability and satisfaction theory [12], students use social media to fulfill certain needs such as seeking and getting emotional support online, which might lead to students' psychological dependence on social media [13].

The more online emotional support provided by social media, the higher the frequency and intensity of online information exchange; and the more emotional support students gain, the more they want to use social media to maintain and increase their level of emotional support [14]. Misusing the good things (i.e., the benefits of using social media) can turn them into bad things (i.e., problematic social media use [15]. To support this idea, several empirical studies suggest that online social support is positively associated with Internet addiction [13], Facebook addiction [16, 17], and addiction to social networking sites [18,19].

Based on the background problems that have been described, this study wanted to find out whether there was a relationship between social media addiction and phubbing behavior in program students. Study of Counseling Guidance of Lambung Mangkurat University.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses quantitative research methods with the type of correlational research. The purpose of this type of correlational research to be achieved in this study is to determine the relationship between two or more variables without making any changes to the data obtained. has one independent variable and one variable of a dependent. The dependent variable (Y) in this study is phubbing behavior and the independent variable is social media addiction (X). The research data collection was carried out using the online survey method. The population in this study were students of Counseling Guidance, Lambung Mangkurat University of 2019, totaling 80 students. The sampling was done by using a simple random sampling technique. The sample size is taken by looking at Isaac and Michael's table with an error rate of 5% to 65 students. Data collection on rubbing and social media addiction was collected using an instrument questionnaire developed by Karadag using a Likert scale [20]. The research data obtained were then analyzed with the help of the SPSS (Statistical Program for Social Science) version 26.0 program. The first step is descriptive analysis and the prerequisite assumption test which includes normality test, linearity test, and homoscedasticity. After testing the assumptions, the next step is to test the hypothesis with simple regression analysis.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Descriptive Analysis The

following are the results of the descriptive analysis in this study.

Table 1. Analysis of Descriptive

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
of Social Media Addiction (X)	65	24	51	37.42	6,272
Phubbing (Y)	65	17	56	37.26	6783

Based on the table above can be seen that the social media addiction variable (X) has a value of at least 24 and a maximum value of 51 of the 65 subjects. The average value of social media addiction 37.42 with a standard deviation 6.272 variable phubbing (Y) has a value of at least 17 and a maximum value of 56. The average of the variable phubbing at 37.26 with a deviation standard of 6.783.

3.2 Assumption Test The

the researcher conducted a test for normality, linearity, and homoscedasticity as a requirement before the effect test was carried out. The results of the normality test showed that the variables of phubbing and social media addiction (sig. = 0.511) were normally distributed (sig. > 0.05). Linearity test results show that phubbing and

social media addiction have a linear relationship marked with a significance value of 0.289 (sig.> 0.05). Passing the homoscedasticity test is marked by a shapescatter plot that spreads and does not form a certain pattern.

Figure 1. Homoscedasticity test results

3.3 Simple Linear Regression Test The

following are the results of a simple linear regression test.

Table 2. Output model summary of simple linear regression test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. An error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.311 ^a	0.197	.082	6,497	2,066

a. Predictors: (Constant), X

b. Dependent Variable: Y

Table 3. Outputcoefficients Simple linear regression.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	24,676	4,911		5,024	.000
social media addiction (x)	.336	.129	.311	2,598	.012

Based on the results of the effect test using simple linear regression analysis techniques obtained a significance value of 0.012 (sig. <0.05) with the value of $R^2 = 0.197$ and a correlation coefficient of 0.311. This shows that there is an effect of social media addiction on phubbing, with the contribution of social media addiction to phubbing by 19.7% (= 19.7). The regression coefficient value that shows a positive number indicates that the influence is positive, where when social media addiction is high, phubbing will be high, and vice versa. Based on the linear regression test table (coefficient) above, the resulting regression equation formula in this study is $Y = 24,676 + 0,336 X$.

The relationship between social media addiction and behavior phubbing in this study found that social media addiction affects phubbing behavior. This means that someone who falls into the opium category criteria on social media can be concluded that the person tends to engage in behavior phubbing, be it a person whether we realize it or not. This is reinforced by the results of the social media addiction questionnaire, namely I check my social media even though there are other things I have to do, I share what I do, what happens with life and momentary events on social media, I follow activities, events moment, popular videos and trending topics on social media, I communicate with my friends via social media rather than talk to them in person and I prefer to use social media instead of watching television has a higher score than other statements.

Referring to the results of the data analysis that has been carried out, it can be stated that the hypothesis proposed by the researcher is accepted, namely that there is a significant relationship between social media addiction and phubbing behavior. This means that when a student has a high intensity in using social media, it will make communication with other people low. If a person has low communication with other people, then

that person is likely to engage in behavior phubbing. Social media use was positively associated with student phubbing behavior and this finding is in line with previous studies [21,22, 11, 20].

According to Fang, there are probably two factors that influence social media addiction, namely 1) student satisfaction with emotional support from social media can make students addicted to social media use and gradually lose control over their use of social media, and therefore ultimately lead to media use. Social problems, according to utility and satisfaction theory [24]. 2) when students receive "Likes" or supportive comments from social media, they report more happiness and higher self-esteem [25], and this positive reinforcement will encourage them to continue using social media and ultimately lead to more social media use problematic [23].

In using social media, it is not uncommon for students to share status, in the form of short sentences or quotes as a form of expression of what they are feeling. The process of sharing stories that involve emotions on social media will ultimately form a sense of comfort in communicating through various existing media, including smartphones. If this happens frequently then this is an interrelated cycle, the more someone has the comfort of using social media, then several reasons make social media so loved.

The social environment can also influence how the behavior phubbing occurs. Certain social environment determines how a person uses his cellphone and social media. According to Chotpiyatasunondh, the action of a person who only concentrates on his cellphone when in a social environment [4]. The convenience obtained using social media and cellphones will ultimately cause a person to have more potential to engage in behavior phubbing. This statement is also supported by Young & Rodgers arguing that it makes someone lazy to communicate in the real world because it feels more fun to communicate with friends online, resulting in a lack of empathy for the surrounding environment [26].

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the description above, the conclusion from the results of this study is that there is a positive relationship between social media addiction and phubbing behavior. The results showed that there was a significant positive relationship between social media and phubbing behavior. The higher the social media, the higher the phubbing behavior. The contribution between cellphone and social media addiction to phubbing behavior was 19.7%. While the remaining 80.3% is another factor not included in the study. Researchers hope that the results of this study can be input for students of the FKIP ULM Counseling Study Program to increase face-to-face communication with the people around them. For the next researcher, the researcher expects the development of the research variable by pairing other variables. Thus, the research results are more developed and can be used as valid reference material for further research development.

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